

UNMASKING AN OLD DRUG – POLYMYXIN B AND HYPOTENSION: A CASE SERIES

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ABSTRACT

The emergence of multidrug-resistant (MDR) gram-negative bacteria has led to an increased risk of hospital-acquired infections, posing significant public health concern, with expected rising mortality rates by 2050. Polymyxins, first discovered in the late 1940s, have regained clinical importance due to their efficacy against these resistant pathogens, despite being abandoned in the 1970s due to nephrotoxicity and neurotoxicity. Recent resurgence in polymyxin use has occurred due to the limited options for treating resistant infections. However, while nephrotoxicity and neurotoxicity are well-documented, hypotension as a side effect has not been widely recognized. This case series presents five patients who developed hypotension shortly after Polymyxin B infusion. In all cases, blood pressure dropped within 30 to 60 minutes of administration, and appropriate clinical measures, including drug withholding, fluid resuscitation, and vasopressor use, were undertaken to stabilize blood pressure. Despite treatment, one

patient could not be revived. The mechanism behind this hypotension may be related to polymyxin-induced histamine release, endothelial disruption, or alteration in vascular smooth muscle tone. Polymyxin B-induced hypotension is not noted in standard pharmacology resources, suggesting this adverse effect is under-recognized. The exact incidence and risk factors for this side effect remain unclear. Further studies are needed to explain the relationship between polymyxin B and hypotension, identify high-risk patients, and develop strategies to prevent this complication. Clinicians should be aware of this potential adverse

effect, particularly in critically ill patients, and monitor hemodynamic parameters closely during polymyxin B administration.

KEYWORDS: Polymyxin B, Hypotension, MDR infections, Blood pressure.

INTRODUCTION

Hospital-acquired infections caused by multidrug-resistant gram-negative bacteria have emerged as a major public health threat in the past decade and the associated worldwide mortality is expected to rise significantly by 2050.^[1,2] Polymyxins, belong to a class of cyclic polypeptides discovered in the late 1940s and represent some of the last treatment options for these infections. Although they were an obsolete drug for decades, but lately have gained importance because of the predominance multidrug resistant gram negative bacterial infections.^[1]

A significant proportion of MDR infection-related mortality is attributed to pathogens such as *Acinetobacter baumannii*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and extended-spectrum β -lactamase (ESBL)-producing Enterobacteriaceae. Polymyxins, first identified in 1947^[2], are cyclic polypeptide antibiotics.^[2] and are produced by *Bacillus Polymyxa*.^[1]

Polymyxins clinical use was discontinued in the 1970s due to their narrow therapeutic window and its potential to cause nephrotoxicity and neurotoxicity. Over 60% of patients who received polymyxins treatment had nephrotoxicity. However, the recent surge in multidrug-resistant infections and the limited availability of effective antibiotics have renewed interest in polymyxins as a treatment option.^[3]

The spectrum of activity of polymyxins encompasses a broad range of gram-negative organisms, including *Klebsiella* spp., *Enterobacter* spp., *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Acinetobacter* spp. *Escherichia coli*, *Salmonella* spp., *Shigella* spp., *Citrobacter* spp., *Yersinia pseudotuberculosis*, *Haemophilus influenzae*, *Pasteurella* spp., *Bordetella pertussis*, and *Legionella pneumophila*.^[4]

Polymyxin B is associated with quite a few side effects of which nephrotoxicity and neurotoxicity are well known. Hypotension as a side effect of polymyxin infusion has not yet been recognized in the product labelling. Standard pharmacological websites also has not documented hypotension as a side effect of polymyxin B infusion (LEXIDRUG).

Case Study/Series

We hereby present a series of 5 patients, who developed hypotension with polymyxin B infusion

Case 1: A 69-year-old male patient who was admitted to the MICU with blood cultures positive for MDR *Enterobacter cloacae* and *Streptococcus hemolyticus* was initiated on polymyxin B at a loading dose of 15 LU, diluted in 250 mL of 5% dextrose and infused over 3 hours. Patient developed hypotension (BP: 90/40 mmHg) within 1 hour of starting polymyxin B. On recognition of hypotension, appropriate measures were taken by the physicians which included stopping the drug, fluid boluses and vasopressor; BP improved to 125/48 mmHg within 30 minutes.

Case 2: An 81-year-old female patient was admitted to the MICU with urosepsis in septic shock. As patient was at risk for MDR organism, she was initiated on polymyxin with a loading dose of 15 LU, diluted in 250 mL of 5% dextrose, infused over 3 hours. However, the patient's hypotension worsened within 1 hour of starting polymyxin B on nor-adrenaline support. Appropriate measures were promptly taken by the intensivist, the drug was withheld, and the patient was managed with fluid resuscitation and incremental vasopressors until stabilization to prior support was achieved. Blood pressure improved from 70/40 mmHg to 120/55 mmHg within 60 minutes.

Case 3: A 63-year-old male patient was admitted to the MICU in septic shock with multiple comorbidities and recent hospital admissions. He was started on MDR cover with polymyxin for the same reasons. Patient was started on polymyxin B at a loading dose of 15 LU, diluted in 250 mL of 5% dextrose, infused over 3 hours. However, the patient developed hypotension within 30mins of starting polymyxin B even while receiving nor-adrenaline support. Appropriate measures were taken by the intensivist, drug was withheld, and the patient was resuscitated with fluid and vasopressors were added until stabilization. Blood pressure improved from 103/38 mmHg to 126/79 mmHg within 30 minutes.

Case 4: A 66-year-old male patient was admitted to MICU with persistent hypotension after intubation requiring vasopressor. Patient was initiated on polymyxin B at a loading dose of 15 LU, diluted in 250 mL of 5% dextrose, infused over 3 hours in view of previous MDR in cultures. However, patient developed hypotension within 30 mins of starting polymyxin B even while receiving noradrenaline support. Appropriate measures were taken by the intensivists, the drug was withheld, and the patient was fluid resuscitated and vasopressor

dose was increased. This patient in spite of persistent efforts could not be revived. Blood pressure worsened to require adrenaline support also.

Case 5: A 75-year-old female patient was admitted to MICU with blood culture positive for MDR *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. The patient was initiated on polymyxin B at a loading dose of 15 LU, diluted in 250 mL of 5% dextrose, infused over 3 hours. However, the patient developed hypotension within 45 mins of starting polymyxin B. Appropriate measures were taken by the intensivist, the drug was withheld, and patient was managed with fluids and vasopressors until stabilization was achieved. Blood pressure improved from 70/40 mmHg to 125/70 mmHg in an hour.

DISCUSSION

Polymyxins were largely abandoned due to concerns regarding nephrotoxicity and neurotoxicity, leaving gaps in understanding their pharmacokinetics and adverse effects. However, with the global rise of multidrug-resistant Gram-negative bacterial infections, polymyxins have regained clinical significance as a last-resort therapy. While nephrotoxicity and neurotoxicity are well-documented, cardiovascular toxicity particularly hypotension has been reported only in a limited number of case reports and small series.^[1,5]

In our case series, we observed that all five patients who received polymyxin B infusion developed hypotension within a short period following administration. This observation was not limited or restricted to any particular brand or batch number and all infusions were given as per standard recommended dilution and time period. Notably, hypotension as an adverse effect of polymyxin B is not documented in standard pharmacology resources such as Lexidrug nor in the drug's product labeling. The most commonly recognized adverse effects of polymyxin B are nephrotoxicity and neurotoxicity, which have been well documented in clinical literature.^[1,5]

A possible mechanism for this observation is the ability of polymyxins to induce histamine release, leading to vasodilation and hypotension. Prior animal studies have demonstrated a correlation between polymyxin-induced histamine release and hypotension.^[6] Additionally, polymyxins have been shown to disrupt endothelial integrity, increasing vascular permeability, which may contribute to hemodynamic instability.^[7] Another hypothesis suggests that polymyxins interact with lipid membranes of vascular smooth muscle cells, altering vascular tone and leading to transient hypotension.^[8]

A previously published case report by Raghavapuram *et al.*, described a similar instance of polymyxin B-induced hypotension, where the patient's blood pressure dropped significantly soon after administration.^[4] Despite this, there remains limited recognition of this adverse effect in the broader literature, and the exact incidence and risk factors remain unclear.

Given our findings and the limited available literature, further investigations are needed to establish a clearer relationship between polymyxin B and hypotension. Clinicians should be aware of this potential adverse effect and closely monitor hemodynamic parameters during polymyxin B infusion, especially in critically ill patients. Future research should focus on identifying patients at higher risk, understanding the underlying mechanisms, and developing preventive strategies to mitigate this complication.

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